

Synthesis of some Thiazole Schiff Bases and Their Derivatives

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Synthesis of some Schiff bases derived from 4,5-diaryl-2-aminothiazoles have been described. Cycloaddition of the Schiff bases with thioglycolic acid gave the corresponding thiazolidone derivatives. Reaction with cyclohexanone gave the secondary amines. The compounds have been characterised by ir and mass spectra, and screened for antifungal activity.

SCHIFF bases play an important role in many biological processes. Their ready synthesis and numerous biological activities¹⁻⁵ contributed greatly to their popularity. From these and related observations it has been suggested that an azomethin linkage is perhaps an essential structural requirement for such activity. In view of these observations, in the present communication we have reported the synthesis of some new Schiff bases from 4,5-disubstituted-2-aminothiazoles and aromatic aldehydes having the structural feature shown below.

2-Amino-4,5-disubstituted-thiazoles were prepared by two different methods, from deoxybenzoin and from desyl chloride. Deoxybenzoins, prepared by the reported⁶ method, were brominated with bromine in chloroform, and the bromo derivatives were condensed with thiourea⁷ to give the desired 2-amino-4,5-disubstituted-thiazoles. In the second method, the required thiazoles were prepared from desyl chlorides⁸ and thiourea. It has been reported⁹ that Schiff bases react with acetophenone to yield secondary amines which exhibit antitumour activity. Cycloaddition of Schiff bases with mercaptoacetic acid results in the formation of thiazolidone derivatives which are particularly interesting as local anaesthetic and anticonvulsant agents¹⁰⁻¹². Owing to the potential medicinal importance of the above type of compounds the Schiff bases prepared were converted to secondary amines and thiazolidone derivatives by treatment with cyclohexanone and mercaptoacetic acid, respectively.

The Schiff bases have been identified by elemental and spectral analysis. Infrared spectra

of Schiff bases show a strong sharp band at 1620-1610 (C=N stretch), and 1605, 1530, 1460 and 1430 cm^{-1} (thiazole and phenyl ring vibrations). The 4-thiazolidones are characterised by a band at 1660-1680 cm^{-1} (NC=O stretch).

The mass spectra fragmentation patterns of two representative members of 4,5-disubstituted-2-aminothiazoles and their corresponding Schiff bases are in good agreement with the suggested structures. 4,5-Disubstituted-2-amino thiazoles have been compared with that of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole in order to determine the nature of substitution at 4- and 5-positions of the thiazole ring. All the Schiff bases and thiazoles give stable molecular ions (the base peak in most of the cases), which undergo fission at the ring nitrogen and the ring carbon bonds. The breaking of 1,2 and 3,4 bonds, and 2,3 and 4,5 bonds of the thiazole ring which was evidenced by several workers¹³⁻¹⁵, can be noticed in all the spectra (a, b, c and d in Scheme 1). Fragments formed by cleavage of 1,2 and 3,4 bonds of the thiazole ring with the charge retained by the sulphur containing portion (Process-b in Scheme 1) undergo the familiar process of fragmentation already described by Metzger¹⁴ and Saint-Ruf¹⁵ only in the case of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole (Scheme 2). All the Schiff bases give abundant $[M-1]^+$ peaks which is formed by the loss of azomethin proton¹⁶. Other characteristic fragments observed arise out of the loss of SH, $[\text{CH}=\text{S}]$, $[\text{SH} \text{ and } \text{CO}]$, OH and CHO radicals from the molecular ion¹⁶. Most of the transitions indicated are justified by appropriate metastable peaks.

Experimental

Ir spectra (nujol) were determined in a Perkin-Elmer 337 grating spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Elemental analysis was performed at Technical University of Munich, West Germany.

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4,5-Diaryl-2-aminothiazoles :

These compounds were prepared by two different methods.

Method A : Deoxybenzoins (1 mol) prepared by the reported method⁶ were brominated with bromine (1.1 mol) in chloroform to give the corresponding monobromo derivative. The brominated product (1 mol) and thiourea (1 mol) were refluxed in absolute ethanol for 3-4 h. Then excess of the solvent was evaporated, the residue was made alkaline by dilute ammonium hydroxide, filtered and the solid recrystallised from ethanol.

Method B : The thiazoles were prepared from desyl chlorides obtained from benzoin or substituted-benzoins⁸ and thiourea as reported in Method A.

M.p., yield and analytical data of the thiazoles are given in Table 1.

Schiff bases derived from 4,5-diaryl-2-aminothiazoles : A mixture of appropriate aminothiazole (1 mol) and aldehyde (1 mol) in ethanol (30-35 ml) and piperidin (3-4 drops) was refluxed in a water-bath for ~1 h. The product was then cooled, and the resulting crystals were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

TABLE I

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 10 ppm
						N	S	
1*	Phenyl	Phenyl	180	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	10.82 (11.11)	12.54 (12.70)	78
2*	4-Methoxyphenyl	4-Methoxyphenyl	195	66	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.58 (8.97)	9.96 (10.25)	70
3*	4-Methoxyphenyl	Phenyl	192	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	9.71 (9.93)	10.98 (11.35)	72
4.	2-Chlorophenyl	2-Chlorophenyl	124	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ SCl ₂	8.32 (8.75)	9.53 (10.00)	78
5.	4-Chlorophenyl	4-Chlorophenyl	160	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ SCl ₂	8.51 (8.75)	9.75 (10.00)	79
6.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	190	60	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₄ S	16.20 (16.57)	9.08 (9.46)	71
7.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	Phenyl	176	52	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	13.63 (14.23)	10.27 (10.84)	70

* Satisfactory C, H analyses obtained.

TABLE 2

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 10 ppm
							N	S	
1.	Phenyl	Phenyl	2-Hydroxy-phenyl	150	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	7.62 (7.86)	8.55 (8.93)	92
2.	Phenyl	Phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	149	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	7.31 (7.56)	8.28 (8.64)	91
3.	Phenyl	Phenyl	4-Dimethyl-aminophenyl	146	68	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ S	10.65 (10.96)	8.01 (8.35)	89
4.	Phenyl	Phenyl	4-Chloro-phenyl	140	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ SCl	7.11 (7.48)	8.14 (8.55)	90
5.	Phenyl	Phenyl	3-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl	185	75	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	7.02 (7.25)	8.03 (8.29)	95
6.	Phenyl	Phenyl	2-Hydroxy-naphthyl	185	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	6.53 (6.86)	7.42 (7.84)	99
7.	Phenyl	Phenyl	Phenyl	170	58	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	7.95 (8.28)	9.08 (9.41)	91
8.	Phenyl	Phenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	170	75	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ ON ₂ SBr	6.18 (6.48)	7.12 (7.35)	98
9.	Phenyl	Phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	175	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ ON ₂ SBr ₂	5.24 (5.44)	5.86 (6.22)	94
10*	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	2-Hydroxy-phenyl	128	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	6.28 (6.78)	7.25 (7.69)	90
11.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	142	69	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	6.14 (6.51)	7.12 (7.44)	91
12.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Dimethyl-aminophenyl	194	66	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.18 (9.48)	6.85 (7.22)	90
13.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	2-Hydroxy-naphthyl	151	68	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.89 (8.97)	6.52 (6.83)	94
14.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	Phenyl	142	56	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	6.56 (7.00)	7.72 (8.00)	92
15.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Chloro-phenyl	187	69	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ SCl	6.08 (6.45)	6.96 (7.37)	95
16.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	140	74	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ SBr	5.18 (5.65)	6.10 (6.46)	90
17.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	160	75	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ SBr ₂	4.56 (4.87)	5.17 (5.57)	91
18*	4-Methoxy-phenyl	Phenyl	2-Hydroxy-phenyl	130	75	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	7.01 (7.25)	7.82 (8.29)	93
19.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	Phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	120	62	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	6.59 (7.00)	7.65 (8.00)	98
20.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	Phenyl	4-Dimethyl-aminophenyl	181	64	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ ON ₂ S	9.77 (10.16)	7.29 (7.74)	92
21.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	Phenyl	2-Hydroxy-naphthyl	164	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	5.94 (6.39)	6.88 (7.30)	94
22.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	Phenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	182	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ SBr	5.75 (6.02)	6.61 (6.88)	98
23.	4-Methoxy-phenyl	Phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	167	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ SBr ₂	4.68 (5.14)	5.59 (5.88)	96
24.	4-Chloro-phenyl	4-Chloro-phenyl	2-Hydroxy-phenyl	155	69	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ SCl ₂	6.21 (6.60)	7.18 (7.54)	97
25.	4-Chloro-phenyl	4-Chloro-phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	100	73	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ ON ₂ SCl ₂ Br	4.36 (4.81)	5.08 (5.49)	98
26.	3-Chloro-phenyl	2-Chloro-phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	186	75	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ ON ₂ SCl ₂ Br	4.48 (4.81)	5.13 (5.49)	97

* Explanation as in Table 1.

M.p., yield and analytical data of the Schiff bases are given in the Table 2.

2-Aryl-3-(4',5'-diarylthiazol-2'-yl)-4-thiazolidones: Schiff bases derived from 2-amino-4,5-diarylthiazoles and substituted benzaldehydes or naphthaldehydes (1 mol) were dissolved in minimum amount of dry benzene, and thioglycolic acid (1.1 mol) was added

to it. The mixture was refluxed for 6 h in a water-bath. The content was cooled and excess of solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The solid residue thus formed was washed thoroughly with water and then with a solution of sodium bicarbonate to remove the residual thioglycolic acid, and the product was recrystallised from ethanol.

M.p., yield and analytical data of the thiazolidones are given in Table 3.

4,5-Diaryl-2-substituted-methylaminothiazoles : Schiff bases derived from 4,5-diaryl-2-aminothiazoles (1 mol) and cyclohexanone (1 mol) in ethanol (30-35 ml) with 3-4 drops of concentrated

HCl was heated under reflux in a water-bath at 70° for ~4 h. The product was then cooled and excess of the solvent was removed. The crystals thus obtained were filtered and were recrystallised from ethanol.

M.p., yield and analytical data are given in Table 4.

TABLE 3

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 10 ppm
							N	S	
1.	Phenyl	Phenyl	2-Hydroxyphenyl	140	77	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	6.14 (6.51)	14.84 (14.89)	74
2.	Phenyl	Phenyl	4-Methoxyphenyl	95	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	5.87 (6.90)	18.92 (14.41)	70
8.	Phenyl	Phenyl	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	115	75	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ N ₂ OS ₂	8.72 (9.19)	18.64 (14.01)	71
4.	Phenyl	Phenyl	4-Chlorophenyl	150	69	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S ₂ Cl	5.81 (6.25)	18.76 (14.29)	78
5.	Phenyl	Phenyl	Phenyl	125	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S ₂	6.28 (6.76)	14.92 (15.46)	78
6.	Phenyl	Phenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	198	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ Br	4.95 (5.50)	12.08 (12.57)	75
7.	Phenyl	Phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	140	75	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ Br ₂	4.29 (4.76)	10.44 (10.88)	75
8.	4-Methoxyphenyl	4-Methoxyphenyl	2-Hydroxyphenyl	118	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	5.26 (5.71)	12.75 (13.06)	72
9.	4-Methoxyphenyl	4-Methoxyphenyl	4-Methoxyphenyl	126	65	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	5.10 (5.55)	12.26 (12.70)	70
10.	4-Methoxyphenyl	4-Methoxyphenyl	2-Hydroxynaphthyl	156	66	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	4.71 (5.16)	11.52 (11.81)	77
11.	4-Methoxyphenyl	4-Methoxyphenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	155	71	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Br	4.48 (4.92)	10.79 (11.25)	72
12.	4-Methoxyphenyl	Phenyl	2-Hydroxyphenyl	168	68	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	6.02 (6.54)	14.48 (14.96)	71
13.	4-Methoxyphenyl	Phenyl	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	98	62	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	8.77 (8.62)	12.69 (12.14)	73
14.	4-Methoxyphenyl	Phenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	170	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Br	4.93 (5.52)	12.17 (12.68)	74
15*	4-Chlorophenyl	4-Chlorophenyl	2-Hydroxyphenyl	222	71	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂	8.60 (8.91)	12.48 (12.85)	75
16.	2-Chlorophenyl	2-Chlorophenyl	2-Hydroxyphenyl	152	68	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂	8.45 (8.91)	12.99 (12.85)	76
17.	2-Chlorophenyl	2-Chlorophenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	144	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂ Br	4.52 (4.85)	10.52 (11.09)	78

* Explanation as in Table 1.

TABLE 4

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		% Inhibition on <i>Curvularia</i> at 10 ppm
							N	S	
1*	Phenyl	Phenyl	Phenyl	110	75	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S	5.97 (6.64)	6.89 (7.39)	72
2.	Phenyl	Phenyl	3-Hydroxyphenyl	107	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	5.71 (6.23)	6.70 (7.12)	71
3.	Phenyl	Phenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	90	68	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ SBr	4.76 (5.90)	5.57 (6.06)	73

(Table 4 contd.)

4.	Phenyl	Phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	101	69	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SBr_2$	4.08 (4.61)	4.81 (5.27)	75
5	Phenyl	Phenyl	4-Dimethylamino-phenyl	210	63	$C_{10}H_{10}ON_2S$	8.29 (8.52)	8.16 (6.72)	74
6*	Phenyl	Phenyl	2-Hydroxynaphthyl	115	58	$C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2S$	5.08 (5.59)	5.88 (6.38)	78
7	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	2-Hydroxyphenyl	216	71	$C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2S$	5.01 (5.50)	5.86 (6.28)	74
8	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	116	72	$C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2SBr$	4.18 (4.76)	5.02 (5.44)	75
9	4-Methoxy-phenyl	4-Methoxy-phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	125	76	$C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2SBr_2$	3.66 (4.19)	4.81 (4.79)	75
10.*	4-Methoxy-phenyl	Phenyl	2-Hydroxyphenyl	121	70	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2S$	5.27 (5.70)	6.10 (6.51)	73
11	2-Chloro-phenyl	2-Chloro-phenyl	2-Hydroxyphenyl	98	68	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SCl_2$	4.96 (5.41)	5.73 (6.18)	76
12	2-Chloro-phenyl	2-Chloro-phenyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	182	74	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SBrCl_2$	4.12 (4.69)	4.92 (5.37)	77
13	2-Chloro-phenyl	2-Chloro-phenyl	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	116	70	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SBr_2Cl_2$	3.68 (4.15)	4.89 (4.74)	79

* Explanation as in Table 1.

Antifungal activity · Poisoned food technique¹⁷ was used for the fungicidal assay. All the compounds reported were tested for toxicity towards *Curvularia* species. The percentage of inhibition of the germination of conidia of test fungus during 48 h was determined by dry-weight method. The test drugs were used at concentrations of 500, 250, 100 and 10 ppm in triplicate. All the compounds in this series are 100% active in a dilution of 500, 250 and 100 ppm. Schiff bases are also very active (88-96%) at a concentration of 10 ppm, whereas the activity of other compounds is less (70-80%) at this concentration. The disappearance of the azomethin linkage by catalytic condensation with cyclohexanone or by thiazolidone formation with thioglycolic acid decreases the fungicidal activity

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